

1 **The polycomb complex in inflammatory bowel disease.**

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8 Epigenetic regulation of gene expression underlies disease pathology and important aspects of medicine
9 that relate to patient outcomes including resistance to clinical interventions. We identified quantitatively
10 significant regulation of polycomb repressive complex 2 (PRC2) components EZH1 and SUZ12 by human
11 NOD2 in a heterologous system. In primary monocytes from humans with Crohn's Disease whose
12 genomes contain a mutation in NOD2, the PRC1 complex component PCGF5 was and we found
13 important changes in expression of SCML1 and SCML2, and related epigenetic plant homeodomain
14 molecules Phf12 and Phf19 were modestly activated. Among the major cellular defects in bone marrow
15 derived immune cells from transgenic NOD2 ^{-/-} (knockout) mice was failure to activate EZH2 in response
16 to gram negative infection in vivo with *N. gonorrhoea*. NOD2 influences polycomb repressive complex
17 activation and its transcriptional regulation is altered in inflammatory bowel disease.
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